

KNOWLEDGE AND BEHAVIOR OF REGULAR STUDENTS TOWARD STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES IN INCLUSIVE SCHOOL

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Abstract:

This research aims to determine the relation between knowledge levels of inclusive education and social behavior of regular students to students with special needs. Method of this research used survey by using sample of 34 students who have students with disabilities as their peers in their class. Data was collected by using questionnaire to determine the relation between knowledge levels of inclusive education and social behavior. Data was analyzed by using bivariate analysis statistic technique to explore the relation between two variables which were guessed related each other. The result of this research is concluded that there is no significant relation between knowledge level of inclusive education and social behavior of regular students to students with disabilities in inclusive school. Regular students need support from school to understand more students with disabilities, so their knowledge can be implemented in the form of suitable behavior.

Keywords: inclusive education, knowledge, behavior, students with disabilities, regular students

Introduction

Inclusive education is one of non-discriminative education service system form that will be implemented in all regular school, namely elementary, junior high school, and senior high school. Hildegun Olsen (Tarmansyah, 2007: 82) states that in inclusive education, school should accommodate every students without consider their physical appearance, intellectual, social emotional, linguistic or another condition. Inclusive education is also an education service for students who have special educational needs in regular school (elementary school, junior high school, senior high school, and vocational high school) and

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called as special in the meaning of disorder, slow learning, or difficult in learning (Marthan, 2007: 145). Indonesia is one of the nation's supporting inclusive education, so the number of inclusive schools increased in the last 5 years. It also needs to be supported in order to create inclusive school suit with its function and objectives.

One of factors supporting inclusive education is students, both students with special needs and regular students. For regular students, to accept their regular school to be changed into inclusive school is a new challenge because regular students will be in the same area with students with special needs. Different characteristic of students with special needs become challenge for regular students. This is in line with statement from Salend (2011) that factors influencing inclusive education are normalization, early intervention and childhood program, technology development, human rights, supporting group, and laws (pg. 14).

Salend (2011) states that the effect of inclusive education is experienced by regular students and students with special needs, teachers, and family (pag. 29). The effect experienced by both regular students and students with special needs is academic and social areas. In academic point of view, students with special needs have good academic ability improvement if they are given suitable curriculum (Black-Hawkins, Florian & Rouse, 2007; Cushing et.al, 2009; Hang & Rabren, 2009; Hehir, 2007). Also from their social, behavior, and attitude side in inclusive school, it is better than students who do not learn in inclusive school (Salend & Garick Duhaney, 2007). But, in social aspect especially related with attitude and behavior, Siperstein, et al (2007) find that regular students have limited interaction with students with special needs in school and they choose not to socialize with them after school. This limited socialization of regular students is because their low knowledge about students with special needs, so they choose to do wrong behavior. Knowledge is product of knowing and it is happened after someone sensed particular object (Notoatmodjo, 2003: 128). Knowledge possessed by a person is gathered and implemented from some steps, namely: 1) Awareness, 2) Interest, 3) Evaluation, 4) Trial, and 5) Adoption (Notoatmodjo, 2003: 128). Whereas, behavior is what an organism do by direct or indirect observation (Notoatmodjo, 2003: 118). Behavior is also affected by some factors: (1) factors that make ease and become basis of particular behavior showed in the form of knowledge, attitude, beliefs, certainty, values and culture, and characteristic of a person, (2) factor that make possible to create particular behavior in the form of physical environment, availability of facility, namely printed media and electronic, medical staff, and (3) factor that support the behavior, namely: argument, support, critic from both family (parents), peers, and teachers. From the definition, it can be concluded that behavior is a response of an organism or person to stimuli coming from outside and can be

observed directly or indirectly. In the other words, person's knowledge can cause new behavior.

From the elaboration above, researcher conduct a research to explore knowledge level and its relation with socialization ability with students with special needs in inclusive school. So, in the future, it can be identified relation between knowledge level and social behavior of regular students to students with special needs. It is important to eliminate obstruction factors to create friendly inclusive school without discrimination.

Method

Participants

The subjects of this research are thirty-four regular students in inclusive school. The subjects were identified as having peer with students with disabilities in their class.

Instrumentation and Procedures

The subjects of this research were asked to fill a number of questionnaire regarding their knowledge and behavior towards students with disabilities. Analysis in this research used bivariate analysis to determine correlation between two variables assumed having relation or correlated each other. This research used two independent variables (Knowledge levels) and dependent variable (socialization behavior). Both variables were tested using category measurement scale; tested by Chi-square, to know p value whether H_0 is accepted or rejected. If $P \text{ Value} < \alpha (0.05)$ then H_0 is rejected. It means that there is significant relation between independent variable and dependent variable.

Results

Data collected through questionnaire was then processed to be distributed based on knowledge levels. Data distribution result of regular students' knowledge about inclusive education is as follows.

Table 3.1: Distribution of regular students' level knowledge about inclusive education

No	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Low	6	17,65%
2	Fairly	22	64,71%
3	Good	6	17,65%
Total		34	100%

Based on Table 3.1, it is known that regular students who have peers with special needs in their class own fairly knowledge about inclusive education (64.61%). There are also students with good knowledge about inclusive education (17.65%) and even have low knowledge levels of inclusive education (17.65%).

For behavior variable, the result is as follows.

Table 3.2: Distribusi Perilaku Siswa Reguler tentang Pendidikan Inklusif

No	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Negative	4	11,76%
2	Neutral	26	76,47%
3	Positive	4	11,76%
Total		34	100%

Based on table 3.1, it is showed that mostly students who have peers with special needs in their class behave neutrally for inclusive education (76.47%). There are also students behave positively about inclusive education (11.76%) and even behave negatively about inclusive education (11.76%).

Result of statistical test of relation between knowledge levels and socialization behavior is as follows.

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
PENG * PER	34	100,0%	0	0,0%	34	100,0%

Based on table Case Processing Summary, it can be seen that there are 34 students on input data. It means, there are no one data which is undetected.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4,220 ^a	4	,377
Likelihood Ratio	4,834	4	,305
Linear-by-Linear Association	3,094	1	,079
N of Valid Cases	34		

a. 8 cells (88,9%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,71.

Based on Chi-Square Test, it can be seen that significant value is 0.149 and Chi-Square value is 0.368. Because of $0.377 > 0.05$, then null hypothesis is accepted. In the other words, there is no relation between knowledge level of inclusive education and socialization behavior of regular students to students with special needs.

Discussion

Based on the result, it is known that there is no significant relation between knowledge levels of inclusive education and socialization behavior of regular students to students with special needs. It is contrary with the statement from Notoatmodjo (2003: 121) that knowledge or cognitive is very important domain in building behavior (overt behavior). Human does activity because of their knowledge and behavior. But, result of data analysis shows that most regular students have fairly knowledge of inclusive education and behave neutrally. It can be said that basically, those students behave suit with their knowledge. This is in line with result of research from Siperstein, et al (2007) showing that regular students do interaction with students with special needs in school and they choose not to do interaction with them outside school.

In research from Haniek (2011), the result also shows that there are no significant relation between knowledge levels and living healthily. This is also in line with another research showing that there is no significant result between knowledge levels and risky behavior of HIV/Aids (Luthfiana, 2012). Those researches support this statement that level of knowledge does not always form behavior of a person.

In inclusive education, regular students should blend in with students with special needs and they have different perceptions (Salend, 2011). This perception cause many different behaviors done by regular students. This is also in line with arguments from Siperstein, et. al (2007) that many students have wrong concept and stereotype view to students with special needs. It causes limited interaction between regular students and students with special needs. This statement is supported by Salend (2011) stating that limited interaction is caused by misperception about students with special needs, so regular students tend to feel pity, afraid, or even mocking.

Based on the elaboration, it can be concluded that knowledge level of inclusive education owned by regular students in inclusive school cannot be implemented yet in their social behavior to students with special needs. It is because regular students do not know about how to treat students with special needs with their characteristics. This problem can be solved by telling them to accept and appreciate students' differences by facilitating the students to become citizen who appreciate differences (Meadan & Monda-Amaya, 2008; Price & Nelson, 2007). Some facility that can be given to regular students

involved with their behavior to visual impairment students is by teaching them about friendship, social ability, making friendly environment for differences, etc. (Salend, 2011).

Salend (2011) also states that there are some ways to create friendship and acceptance of regular students to students with special needs in inclusive environment, namely:

1. It needs teachers' role in inclusive school to teach students of how to accept diversity, how to treat students with special needs. Teachers are role model for students, so teachers' attitude will be copied by students.
2. Cerve (2008), Jordan (2008), and Killen (2009) state that disability stimuli can be done to increase empathy because regular students experienced of how it feels to have disability.
3. Invite speaker to lecture about inclusive education and children with special needs as form of socialization. Chadsey and Gun Han (2005) through their research state that by inviting speaker having special needs can give direct experience for regular students to have experience.
4. Use film, video as media to learn and understand students with special needs. So many films and videos telling about effort and experience of children with special need in daily life. Those media can be used to support regular students in understanding and knowing about their experience, obstacles, and desire of children with special needs when they socialize in community.

Some ways above can be implemented in inclusive school as a way to create empathy, knowledge, and information in understanding characteristic of children with special needs, so behavior of regular students to students with special needs can be improved well and properly.

Conclusion

Based on the discussion above, the conclusion is that there is no significant correlation between knowledge levels of inclusive education and socialization behavior of regular students in inclusive school. Regular students need support from school in order to be more understanding about students with special needs, so their knowledge can be implemented in the form of proper behavior.

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